

Evaluation of the Efficacy of the Mini Parasep SF Faecal Parasite Concentrator; A New Technique against the Direct Smear and Formol Ether Concentration Technique for the Detection of Intestinal Parasites in Stool.

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ABSTRACT

The efficacy of Mini Parasep, a new faecal Parasite Concentrator developed by the company DiaSys Europe Limited (formerly Intersep Ltd) was evaluated alongside the modified Formol ether concentration and direct smear techniques using 120 stool samples in Calabar, Nigeria between May and June, 2011. The manufacturer's instruction was strictly followed in the evaluation of the new test while standard procedures were used for the direct smear and the FECT. Of the three methods, FECT was most efficient in the detection of intestinal parasite (57.5%) and was closely followed by the Mini Parasep method (50.0%). There was no statistically significant difference at the rate which the two methods detected intestinal parasitic infections ($P>0.05$). On the contrary, the Mini Parasep and the FECT methods detected more intestinal infections than the direct smear (28.3%). The difference in both cases were statistically significant ($P<0.05$). Both the Mini Parasep and the FECT detected 30.2% and 40.7% respectively of infections that were negative with the direct smear. The difference in the detection rate of infection by the two methods was not statistically significant ($P>0.05$). All the samples that were positive by direct smear for intestinal parasites were also positive by the Mini Parasep and FECT. The FECT was more efficient in detecting helminth infections while the Mini Parasep performed better in detecting protozoan infection. The Mini Parasep was simple, user-friendly and involves working in an enclosed system with little or no danger of acquiring infection while the FECT is more labour-intensive with potent danger of acquiring infection and outbreak of fire because of the use of ether in an "open" system. The result of this study has confirmed that the Mini Parasep is efficient for the detection of intestinal parasites. We recommend the adoption of the Mini Parasep method because of its simple and safe technology and efficacy, since most of our laboratories are not currently using the FECT for the diagnosis of intestinal parasites.

Keywords: Evaluation, Mini Parasep, Formol ether, Direct Smear, Techniques.

INTRODUCTION

Intestinal parasitic infections constitute a greater bulk of the Neglected Tropical Diseases (NTDs). The approximate global prevalence, death and disability-adjusted life years (DALYs) are 800 million, 3000-30,000 and 1.2-10.5 for *Ascaris lumbricoides*, 600 million, 3000-65,000 and 1.8-22.1 million for Hookworm and 600million, 3000-10,000 and 1.6-6.4 million for *Trichuris trichiura* respectively (1). Intestinal protozoan infections such as amoebiasis and giardiasis are also a source of great concern because of the high morbidity associated with them in the tropics.

All these agents are endemic in Nigeria. Children and pregnant women are particularly vulnerable to these infections. In a study conducted in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State on the epidemiology of gastrointestinal helminthes, Ikon and Useh (2) reported a prevalence of 65% among pupils, with those in sub-urban schools having a higher prevalence of 75.3% than those in urban schools (54.7%).

Other studies have equally affirmed the endemicity of intestinal parasitic infections in Nigeria. In a study conducted in Uga, Anambra State, 50.6% of school children were infected with intestinal parasites with hookworm having

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the highest prevalence of 48.2% (3). In a related study in Ibule Soro, Ondo State of Nigeria, intestinal parasitic infections were confirmed in 40.9% of pupils studied. The most prevalent was *A. lumbricoides* with a prevalence of 14.9% (4). Akogun and Badaki reported on the high endemicity of these parasites along the Benue River Valley in Adamawa State (5). In Zimbabwe, Midzi *et al.* (6) also confirmed the high prevalence of intestinal parasitic infections.

Several factors are responsible for the high endemic levels of these parasites in the tropics. Among these include indiscriminate disposal of waste, use of faeces as fertilizers, dispersal of ova and cysts of parasites by flood occasioned by heavy rains and warm weather which ensures the viability of cysts and ova. Other factors include poverty, illiteracy, non-availability of skilled manpower to handle the diagnosis of intestinal parasitic infection, lack of political will and finance to embark on helminth de-worming programmes. The other impediment is the procedure adopted by different medical laboratories for the detection of infective stages of intestinal parasites (7).

In Nigeria, all medical laboratories are known to use the direct smear technique which involves the microscopic examination of faeces prepared in saline and Lugol's iodine routinely for the diagnosis of intestinal infections. In addition to this, some laboratories also perform a concentration technique, particularly the brine flotation technique to increase the chances of the isolation of ova of *Ascaris lumbricoides* and hookworm. The efficiency of the brine flotation technique in detecting intestinal poly-parasitism from stool samples was compared separately with those of direct smear and formol-ether concentration technique (FECT), using the combination of three methods as reference in a study in Calabar, Nigeria (8). The combination technique, direct smear, brine flotation and formol-ether detected intestinal parasites at the frequencies of 33.4%, 26.6%, 30.5% and 28.0% respectively. Although, the formol ether technique is often used as the gold

standard, brine was more efficient in detecting helminth eggs. The FECT on the other hand was more efficient in the detection of protozoan cysts. Elsewhere, a new technique known as the FLOTAC has been assessed alongside triplicate Kato-Katz technique for its efficiency in the detection of helminth parasites (9). Considering the pooled results of both methods as diagnostic "gold standard", the observed prevalence of *Trichuris trichiura*, hookworm and *A. lumbricoides* were 63.4, 33.8 and 22.9%, respectively. The sensitivity of examining a single stool sample by FLOTAC for diagnosing *T. trichiura*, hookworm and *A. lumbricoides* was 88.7, 83.0 and 82.8%, respectively. Lower sensitivities were observed for Kato-Katz even after examining three samples. Knopp *et al* (10) also associated the FLOTAC technique with higher rates of sensitivities as compared to Kato-Katz.

In this study, we have compared the efficacy of a new method of faecal concentration know as Biohit Mini Parasep Faecal Concentrator with the direct smear and the conventional FECT as modified by Ridley-Allen. Parasep is a commercial kit developed by DiaSys Europe Limited (formerly Intersep Ltd). It is an enclosed, single use, disposable system. Its performance benefits include optimum sample recovery, enhanced sample clarity, a rapid four step process, and optimization of human resources and the reduction of human error. This technique has been evaluated against the FECT by Kettelhut *et al.* (11). It gave a similar rate of recovery of parasites and negligible interference in the amount of debris present in the deposit. They also reported a significant increase in the recovery of certain parasites namely *Taenia* species and *Hymenolepis nana*. An evaluation of this method has not been conducted and published in the literature in Nigeria to the knowledge of these authors. The main aim and objective of this study was to assess the efficiency of this new technique against the direct smear and EFCT approaches being used by some medical laboratories in Nigeria for the detection of intestinal parasites. An evaluation of the cost

element alongside the technical results would give an informed opinion on the utilization of the technique under consideration.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Area and Subjects

The study was conducted at the Parasitology Laboratory of the Department of Medical Microbiology/Parasitology of the University of Calabar Teaching Hospital, Calabar, Nigeria. One hundred and twenty stool samples collected in clean universal containers from pupils of State Housing Primary School, Atekong Street, Calabar following the consent of the school authority and parents/guardians were investigated for the presence of intestinal parasites using the direct smear, FECT and the Mini Parasep method.

Processing of Samples

The Parasep Faecal parasite concentrator employs the principle of the Ridley-Allen formol-ether sedimentation technique (12) in a closed system. It consists of a mixing chamber in which the faeces is mixed with 10% formalin. The ether or ethyl acetate is added (1 drop of Triton-X is added to the mixture when ethyl acetate is used as it helps to break up the faecal matter) and Parasep is immediately sealed by screwing the filtrate/thimble sedimentation cone onto the mixing chamber. The seal is an air/liquid seal which prevents the release of biohazardous material. There is also a safety lock to ensure that the mixing chamber and the filter thimble are removed together for safe disposal. The mixture is vortexed and Parasep is then inverted to allow the mixture to be filtered through the filter thimble. The filter thimble is made from high density polyethylene and has a 2 stage filtration matrix which means that the large particles are rejected without occluding the 425µm pores. There is also a debris trap so that rejected particles are trapped to prevent extrusion into the sedimentation cone. Parasep is then centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 1 minute. The mixing chamber and filter thimble are unscrewed

and discarded. There is an ether/ethyl acetate layer, fatty plug, formalin and sediment as is obtainable in the FECT. Examination of the deposit is done for the presence of ova, cysts and larvae.

For the direct smear preparation, a representative portion of the well-mixed stool sample was emulsified in a drop of saline and iodine on a grease free slide. The FECT was used alongside the direct smear to assess the efficacy of the Mini Parasep method. The modified formol ether technique was used in the study (12). Briefly, about 2gm of faeces was emulsified in 7ml of 10% formol saline in a centrifuge tube, using a swab stick. The mixture was passed through a sieve. It was replaced in a centrifuged tube and 3 ml of ether added, and shaken vigorously for about 30 seconds, the tube was spun at 3000 rpm for about 3 minutes. The fatty deposit at the interface of the liquids was loosened with a glass rod and the tube quickly inverted at an angle of 45°. The deposit was examined for the presence of intestinal parasites.

Data Analysis

The data generated in the study were analyzed using the Chi-squared test with Yates' correction to cater for the low sample size. The level of significance was $P < 0.05$.

RESULTS

Table 1 is based on the frequency of recovery of intestinal parasites by the methodology used in the study. The highest rate of recovery of intestinal parasites occurred with FECT (57.5%) following in descending order by Mini Parasep (50.0%) and lastly by Direct Smear (28.3%). There was a statistically significant difference at the rate at which each of the three procedures detected intestinal parasitic infection (Yates' $X^2 = 20.88$, $df: 2$, $P = 0.0002927$). Similarly the difference in the rate at which the FECT was able to detect intestinal parasitic infection in comparison to the direct smear method was statistically significant

(Yates' $X^2 = 19.661$, $P=0.0000029$). Relatedly, there was a statistically significant difference between the rate at the Mini Parasep detected intestinal parasitic infection compared to the direct smear approach (Yates' $X^2 = 10.93$, $P=0.0000094$). Although the FECT detected more infections (57.5%) than the Mini Parasep (50.0%), the difference in the rate of detection was not statistically significant $X^2 = 1.358$, $P=0.243$).

The rate of detection of intestinal parasites from samples that were negative for parasites by direct smear is shown on Table 2. FECT detected more parasites 35(40.7%) than the Mini Parasep method (30.2%). However, the difference in the rate of detection was not statistically significant (Yates $X^2 = 1.626$, $P=0.2022$).

On Table 3 is shown, the rate of detection of intestinal parasites from faecal samples that were positive by direct smear. Both methods were able to detect all the positive cases detected by direct smear. Figure 1 depicts the rate of detection of each specific intestinal parasite by the different methods used in the study. Of the three methods used, FECT was more efficient in the detection of helminth parasites followed in all cases by Mini Parasep. The direct smear method was the least efficient. This applied to common endemic helminth parasites such *Ascaris lumbricoides*, hookworm and *Trichuris trichiura*. The Mini Parasep method performed better in the detection of protozoan parasites. It detected more cases of *Giardia intestinalis* than the FECT. The FECT and Mini Parasep had the same rate of detection

of *E. nana*.

H^a = Hookworm; A I = *Ascaris lumbricoides*; T i = *Trichuris trichiura*; E h = *Entamoeba histolytica*; E n = *Endolimax nana*; G i = *Giardia intestinalis*; I b = *Iodoamoeba butschlii*.

Table 1: Frequency of recovery of intestinal Parasites by the methodology used in the study.

Methodology	No. of Samples Examined	No. (%) Positive
Direct Smear	120	34(28.3)
Formol Ether Concentration Technique (FECT)	120	69(57.5)
Mini Parasep SF	120	60(50.0)

Table 2: Rate of detection of intestinal Parasite from 86 samples that were negative for parasites by Direct Smear.

Method	No. (%) Positive
FECT	35(40.7)
Mini Parasep SF	26(30.2)

Table 3: Rate of isolation of intestinal Parasites from 34 Faecal Samples that were positive by Direct Smear.

Methodology	No. (%) Positive
FECT	34(100)
Mini Parasep SF	34(100)

DISCUSSION

The morbidity control of helminth infection is founded on the principle of “preventive chemotherapy” (13-15). This involves the treatment of the most vulnerable group like school children with broad spectrum anthelmintic drugs such as albendazole through the school system. The health benefits derived from such regular periodic de-worming exercise cannot be over-emphasized. Such treatments apart from giving relief to the infected subjects are also known to improve school attendance and performance as well as reverse growth retardation (16,17). This is particularly applicable in community-based control programmes. However, this does not in any way eliminate or reduce the significance of diagnosing or detecting the presence of the actual intestinal agents responsible for specific disorders particularly in the hospital setting. Even though, the development of drug resistance to intestinal parasites is not a worrisome phenomenon for now, diagnosis is very crucial for the purpose of surveillance. This informs the continuing search for user-friendly methods such as the FLOTAC and the Mini Parasep.

The formol ether concentration technique has been widely accepted as the gold standard for the detection of protozoan cysts and helminth ova. This is based on the fact that the fat present in stool which impedes the visualization of parasites are lysed with a concomitant fixation of the parasites in formalin. The sedimentation of the preparation helps to pool the parasite to the deposit thereby enhancing the chances of recovery of parasites. The Mini Parasep Faecal Concentrator operates on the same principle but is more user friendly and safer.

Overall, we have demonstrated that the Mini Parasep was highly efficient in the detection of intestinal parasite. With this method, infection was detected at a rate of 50% compared to the 57% obtained when FECT was used. However, the slight difference in the detection rate of infection was not statistically

significant ($X^2 = 1.073$, $df 1$, $P=0.243$). Our findings are related to that of Kettelhut *et al* (11) which associated the Mini Para with a similar rate of recovery of parasite like the FECT but with negligible interference in the amount of debris present in the deposit. The higher yield by the other group may have to do with the fact that already known positive samples were evaluated along with known negative examples. In the present study “virgin” samples were involved.

Currently, it can be safely assumed that the FECT is more or less a research tool for the diagnosis of intestinal infection in Nigeria and other countries in the developing world. Most parasitology laboratories are not applying FECT due to the fact that ether is used in the “open” unlike the Parasep approach where ether is used in an enclosed system. Ether is highly inflammable and could pose great fire hazard in a typical “general purpose laboratory” in the developing world. There is the danger of acquiring infection with FECT approach unlike the use once and discard method adopted in Mini Parasep. Among the 86 samples that were negative by direct smear, Mini Parasep detected intestinal parasitic infection in 30.2% compared to FECT with a higher detection rate of 40.7%. The difference in the rate of detection between the two methods was not statistically significant ($P>0.05$). The implication of these findings is that many infections are diagnosed as negatives when they are actually positive due to the limitation of using direct smear. This makes using the FECT or Mini Parasep compelling.

In this study, all the samples that were positive by direct smear were also positive by the FECT and the Mini Parasep method. No larvae of nematode such as *Strongyloides* or trophozoite of protozoan parasite were encountered in the direct smear. With this, we could not assess the usefulness of the new method in the detection of trophozoite and larvae.

Unlike the study conducted in the United Kingdom (11), we could not evaluate the benefit of using the Mini Parasep to detect trematode and cestode infections in our setting. These are not particularly endemic parasites in

this region. However the former (11) associated the Mini Parasep method with a significant increase in the recovery of certain parasites namely *Taenia* species and *Hymenolepis nana*. We were able to confirm that the Mini Parasep performed better in the detection of intestinal protozoan infections like *G. intestinalis* and *E. nana* (Figure 1). At this point, it is not possible to proffer the actual reason responsible for the better performance of Mini Parasep in the detection of intestinal protozoa. Perhaps, the relative difference in the specific gravity of the mixture may be responsible for this observation. A major limiting factor in this study was the sample size used. A larger sample size would have given us the opportunity of testing various variables to fully assessed the efficacy of the Mini Parasep faecal concentrator. In conclusion, we have found the Mini Parasep Faecal Concentrator to be simple, user-friendly and highly efficient in the detection of common endemic intestinal parasitic infections in the developing world. We are therefore inclined to recommend the routine usage of this technique in our medical laboratories for the detection of intestinal parasites. However more efforts are required to evaluate their effectiveness in the detection of cestodes and trematodes.

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